

Fig. S2. Morphometric PCA plot of 212 flowering plants in the California Floristic Province (CFP) for nine informative traits in paired analysis of *C. howellii* (purple triangles), putative *C. howellii* (downward lavender triangles), and *C. quamash* ssp. *breviflora* (blue circles). Traits in Appendix 2; species and site codes in Table 1, and Figure 2 map.